

A STUDY ON L-FUZZY NORMAL SUB ℓ -GROUP

¹K.Sunderrajan, ²A.Senthilkumar and ³R.Muthuraj

¹SRMV College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore-641020, Tamilnadu, India.

²SNS College of Technology, Coimbatore-641035, Tamilnadu, India.

³H.H.The Rajah's College, Pudukkottai-Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT

This paper contains some definitions and results of L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group and its generalized characteristics.

KEYWORDS

Fuzzy set, L-fuzzy set, L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group, L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group.

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1.INTRODUCTION

L. A. Zadeh[11] introduced the notion of fuzzy subset of a set S as a function from X into $I = [0, 1]$. Rosenfeld[2] applied this concept in group theory and semi group theory, and developed the theory of fuzzy subgroups and fuzzy subsemigroupoids respectively J.A.Goguen [6] replaced the valuations set $[0, 1]$, by means of a complete lattice in an attempt to make a generalized study of fuzzy set theory by studying L-fuzzy sets.. In fact it seems in order to obtain a complete analogy of crisp mathematics in terms of fuzzy mathematics, it is necessary to replace the valuation set by a system having more rich algebraic structure. These concepts ℓ -groups play a major role in mathematics and fuzzy mathematics. G.S.V Satya Saibaba [9] introduced the concept of L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group and L-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of ℓ -group. In this paper, we initiate the study of L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -groups .

2.PRELIMINARIES

This section contains some definitions and results to be used in the sequel.

2.1. Definition [5,6,7]

A lattice ordered group (ℓ -group) is a system $G = (G, *, \leq)$ where

- i $(G, *)$ is a group
- ii (G, \leq) is a lattice
- iii the inclusion is invariant under all translations
 $x \rightarrow a + x + b$ i.e. $x \leq y \Rightarrow a + x + b \leq a + y + b$, for all $a, b \in G$.

2.2 .Definition [11]

Let X be a non-empty set. A fuzzy subset A of X is a function $A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

2.3. Definition [1,2]

An L -fuzzy subset A of G is called an L -fuzzy subgroup (ALFS) of G if for every $x, y \in G$,

- i. $A(xy) \geq A(x) \vee A(y)$
- ii. $A(x^{-1}) = A(x)$.

2.4. Definition [9,10]

An L -fuzzy subset A of G is said to be an L -fuzzy sub ℓ - group(LFS ℓ) of G if for any $x, y \in G$

- i. $A(xy) \geq A(x) \vee A(y)$
- ii. $A(x^{-1}) = A(x)$
- iii. $A(x \vee y) \geq A(x) \vee A(y)$
- iv. $A(x \wedge y) \geq A(x) \vee A(y)$.

2.5. Definition [4]

Let G and G' be any two groups. Then the function $f: G \rightarrow G'$ is said to be a homomorphism if $f(xy) = f(x) f(y)$ for all x, y in G .

2.6.Definition[3]

Let G and G' be any two groups (not necessarily commutative). Then the function $f: G \rightarrow G'$ is said to be an anti-homomorphism if $f(xy) = f(y) f(x)$ for all x, y in G .

Remark: A homomorphism may or may not be an anti-homomorphism

2.7 .Definition [8,10]

A sub ℓ -group H of an ℓ - group G is called a normal sub ℓ -group of G if for all x in G and h in H we have $xhx^{-1} \in H$.

2.8.Definition[8,10]

An L -fuzzy sub ℓ -group A of G is called an L -fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group (LFNS ℓ G) of G if for every $x, y \in G$, $A(xyx^{-1}) \geq A(y)$.

3. PROPERTIES OF AN L-FUZZY NORMAL SUB ℓ -GROUP

In this section, we discuss properties of an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group

3.1.Theorem

Let G be an ℓ -group and A be an L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group of G , then the following conditions are equivalent.

- i. A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of G .
- ii. $A(xy x^{-1}) = A(y)$, for all $x, y \in G$.
- iii. $A(xy) = A(yx)$, for all $x, y \in G$.
- iv.

Proof:

$$i \Rightarrow ii.$$

Let A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of G .

Then $A(xy x^{-1}) \geq A(y)$ for all $x, y \in G$. By taking advantage of the arbitrary property of x , we have,

$$A(x^{-1}y(x^{-1})^{-1}) \geq A(y).$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} A(y) &= A(x^{-1}(xy x^{-1})(x^{-1})^{-1}) \\ &= A(xy x^{-1}) \\ &\geq A(y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} A(xy x^{-1}) &= A(y) \text{ for all } x, y \in G. \\ &ii \Rightarrow iii. \end{aligned}$$

Let $A(xy x^{-1}) = A(y)$, for all $x, y \in G$.

Taking yx instead of y , we get,

$$\begin{aligned} A(xy) &= A(yx), \text{ for all } x, y \in G. \\ &iii \Rightarrow i. \end{aligned}$$

Let $A(xy) = A(yx)$, for all $x, y \in G$.
 $A(xy x^{-1}) = A(yx x^{-1}) = A(y) \geq A(y)$.

Hence, A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of G .

3.2 .Theorem

Let A be an L-fuzzy subset of an ℓ -group G. If $A(e) = 1$ and $A(xy^{-1}) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y)$, $A(x \vee y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y)$, $A(x \wedge y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y)$ and $A(xy) = A(yx)$, for all x and y in G, then A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of a group G, where e is the identity element of G.

Proof:

Let e be identity element of G and x and y in G.

Let $A(e) = 1$ and $A(xy^{-1}) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y)$, for all x and y in G.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } A(x^{-1}) &= A(ex^{-1}) \\ &\geq A(e) \wedge A(x) \\ &\geq 1 \wedge A(x) \\ &= A(x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $A(x^{-1}) \geq A(x)$, for all x in G.

Hence, $A((x^{-1})^{-1}) \geq A(x^{-1})$ and $A(x) \geq A(x^{-1})$.

Therefore, $A(x^{-1}) = A(x)$, for all x in G.

Now, replace y by y^{-1} , then

$$\begin{aligned} A(xy) &= A(x(y^{-1})^{-1}) \\ &\geq A(x) \wedge A(y^{-1}) \\ &= A(x) \wedge A(y), \text{ for all x and y in G.} \\ A(xy) &\geq A(x) \wedge A(y), \text{ for all x and y in G.} \end{aligned}$$

Also, we have, $A(x \vee y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y)$, $A(x \wedge y) \geq A(x) \wedge A(y)$.

Hence, A is an L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G.

Since, $A(xy) = A(yx)$ for all x and y in G, A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G.

3.3 .Theorem

If A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G, then $H = \{x / x \in G: A(x) = 1\}$ is either empty or a normal sub ℓ -group of G.

Proof

It is clear from theorem 3.2

3.4 .Theorem

If A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G, then $H = \{x \in G : A(x) = A(e)\}$ is either empty or a normal sub ℓ -group of G, where e is the identity element of G.

Proof

Since , H is a sub ℓ -group of G.

Now, let for any x in G and y in H, $A(xyx^{-1}) = A(y) = A(e)$.

Since A is an LFNS ℓ G of an ℓ -group G and $y \in H$.

Hence, $xyx^{-1} \in G$ and H is a normal sub ℓ -group of G.

Hence, H is either empty or a normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G.

3.5 .Theorem

If A and B are two L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -groups of an ℓ -group G, then their intersection $A \cap B$ is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of G.

Proof

Let x and y belong to G.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i.} \quad (A \cap B)(xy) &= A(xy) \wedge B(xy) \\ &\geq \{ A(x) \wedge A(y) \} \wedge \{ B(x) \wedge B(y) \} \\ &\geq \{ A(x) \wedge B(x) \} \wedge \{ A(y) \wedge B(y) \} \\ &= (A \cap B)(x) \wedge (A \cap B)(y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(A \cap B)(xy) \geq (A \cap B)(x) \wedge (A \cap B)(y)$, for all x and y in G.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii.} \quad (A \cap B)(x^{-1}) &= A(x^{-1}) \wedge B(x^{-1}) \\ &= A(x) \wedge B(x) \\ &= (A \cap B)(x). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(A \cap B)(x^{-1}) = (A \cap B)(x)$, for all x in G.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{iii.} \quad (A \cap B)(x \vee y) &= A(x \vee y) \wedge B(x \vee y) \\ &\geq \{ A(x) \wedge A(y) \} \wedge \{ B(x) \wedge B(y) \} \\ &\geq \{ A(x) \wedge B(x) \} \wedge \{ A(y) \wedge B(y) \} \\ &= (A \cap B)(x) \wedge (A \cap B)(y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(A \cap B)(x \vee y) \geq (A \cap B)(x) \wedge (A \cap B)(y)$, for all x and y in G.

$$\text{iv.} \quad (A \cap B)(x \vee y) = A(x \vee y) \wedge B(x \vee y)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \{ A(x) \wedge A(y) \} \wedge \{ B(x) \wedge B(y) \} \\ &\geq \{ A(x) \wedge B(x) \} \wedge \{ A(y) \wedge B(y) \} \\ &= (A \cap B)(x) \wedge (A \cap B)(y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(A \cap B)(x \vee y) \geq (A \cap B)(x) \wedge (A \cap B)(y)$, for all x and y in G .

Hence, $A \cap B$ is an L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } (A \cap B)(xy) &= A(xy) \wedge B(xy) \\ &= A(yx) \wedge B(yx), \text{ since } A \text{ and } B \text{ are LFNS } \ell \text{ G of } G. \\ &= (A \cap B)(yx). \\ (A \cap B)(xy) &= (A \cap B)(yx). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $A \cap B$ is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G .

Remark

The intersection of a family of L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -groups of an ℓ -group G is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G .

3.6 .Theorem

If A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G if and only if $A(x) = A(y^{-1}xy)$, for all $x, y \in G$.

Proof

Let x and y be in G . Let A be an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } A(y^{-1}xy) &= A(y^{-1}yx) \\ &= A(ex) \\ &= A(x). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $A(x) = A(y^{-1}xy)$, for all x and y in G .

Conversely, assume that $A(x) = A(y^{-1}xy)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } A(xy) &= A(xyxx^{-1}) \\ &= A(yx) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $A(xy) = A(yx)$, for all x and y in G .

Hence, A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G .

3.7 .Theorem

Let A be an L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G with $A(y) < A(x)$, for some x and y in G, then A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G.

Proof

Let A be an L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G.

Given $A(y) < A(x)$, for some x and y in G,

$$\begin{aligned} A(xy) &\geq A(x) \wedge A(y), \text{ as A is an LFS } \ell \text{ G of G} \\ &= A(y); \text{ and} \\ A(y) &= A(x^{-1}xy) \\ &\geq A(x^{-1}) \wedge A(xy) \\ &\geq A(x) \wedge A(xy), \text{ as A is an LFS } \ell \text{ G of G} \\ &= A(xy). \\ A(y) &\geq A(xy) \geq A(y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $A(xy) = A(y)$, for all x and y in G.

and, $A(yx) \geq A(y) \wedge A(x)$, as A is an LFS ℓ G of G
 $= A(y)$; and

$$\begin{aligned} A(y) &= A(yxx^{-1}) \\ &\geq A(yx) \wedge A(x^{-1}) \\ &\geq A(yx) \wedge A(x), \text{ as A is an LFS } \ell \text{ G of G} \\ &= A(yx). \\ A(y) &\geq A(yx) \geq A(y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $A(yx) = A(y)$, for all x and y in G.

Hence, $A(xy) = A(y) = A(yx)$, for all x and y in G.

Hence, $A(xy) = A(yx)$, for all x and y in G.

Hence, A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group of G.

3.8 .Theorem

Let A be an L-fuzzy sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G with $A(y) > A(x)$ for some x and y in G, then A is an L-fuzzy normal sub ℓ -group of an ℓ -group G.

Proof

It is clear from theorem 3.7

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